

HEXAGON MODEL AND CYBER SECURITY THREAT IN THE LISTED COMMERCIAL BANKS IN NIGERIA

Ugwu, Hope Ifeyinwa and Egbunike, Patrick A.

Department of Accountancy, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19450788>

Abstract: *The study examined the effect of hexagon model on cyber security threat in listed commercial banks in Nigeria. The specific objective was to ascertain the extent to which pressure and opportunity affect cyberfraud in commercial banks in Nigeria. The population comprised 43,583 employees of the listed commercial banks in Nigeria with international authorization; Access Bank, Fidelity Bank, FCMB, First Bank, GTB, UBA and Zenith Bank. Using Taro Yamane's formula, a sample size of 396 respondents was determined and selected through stratified sampling to ensure proportional representation. Data were collected using a structured, Likert-scale questionnaire distributed electronically. Data analysis was conducted using both descriptive statistics and inferential methods, including Pearson's correlation and multiple regression analysis, to explore the predictive strength between the Hexagon Model variables and cybersecurity threats at 5% significance level. The findings revealed that: pressure has a positive and significant effect on cyberfraud in the listed commercial banks in Nigeria ($\beta = 0.182, p = 0.000$); opportunity positively and significantly affects cyberfraud in the listed commercial banks in Nigeria ($\beta = 0.173, p = 0.000$). The study recommends that internal auditors and cybersecurity teams must conduct frequent risk assessments and tighten internal controls, especially those related to access to sensitive financial systems and customer data. Implementing strict role-based access control and continuous monitoring can minimize the opportunities for internal actors to exploit system loopholes or bypass procedures to commit cyberfraud.*

Keywords: Hexagon Model, Pressure, Opportunity and Cybersecurity

1.0 Introduction

The banking industry has experienced a rapid transformation over the past few decades, driven by technological advancements that have reshaped how financial transactions are conducted. In today's global economy, commercial banks are highly dependent on digital infrastructure to deliver their services. From online banking and mobile applications to automated teller machines (ATMs) and cloud-based storage of financial data, technology is at the core of banking operations. However, Kamuangu (2024) argued that the extensive reliance on digital systems has also heightened the risks associated with cyber security threats. In fact, banks are particularly vulnerable to cyber-attacks due

to the sensitive nature of the data they handle, which includes personal information, financial records, and transaction histories (Meduri, 2024). As a result, cybercriminals are constantly developing sophisticated methods to exploit security weaknesses in banking systems, thereby threatening the stability and reputation of financial institutions (Oloidi, 2019). The increasing prevalence of cyber-attacks has necessitated the development of robust strategies to mitigate these threats and safeguard critical banking infrastructure. In this context, the hexagon model, a conceptual framework initially developed for understanding criminal behaviour, offers useful hints into how banks can enhance their cyber security posture by addressing key factors that contribute to organizational vulnerabilities.

The hexagon model offers a structured approach to understanding how cyber security threats can be mitigated by addressing the root causes of organizational vulnerability. Each of the model's six dimensions can be directly linked to common cyber security challenges faced by commercial banks. The "pressure" dimension, for instance, may reflect external pressures such as economic downturns, regulatory changes, or competitive threats that can incentivize cybercriminals to target financial institutions. It can also represent internal pressures, such as employee dissatisfaction or financial difficulties, which can lead to insider threats (Jajere, et'al, 2025). The "opportunity" dimension focuses on the presence of vulnerabilities within an organization's IT infrastructure, including outdated software, weak passwords, and unpatched systems. Cybercriminals constantly seek opportunities to exploit these weaknesses (Santoso, 2019), making it essential for banks to proactively identify and address potential security gaps. The "rationalization" dimension involves the justifications that cybercriminals or insiders may use to justify their actions, such as believing that they are "righting a wrong" or that their actions will go undetected. The "capability" dimension addresses the technical skills and resources that threat actors possess to carry out cyber-attacks. As cybercriminals become more sophisticated, banks must ensure that their security measures are equally advanced. Finally, the "arrogance" dimension refers to the sense of entitlement or superiority that some individuals may feel. A strong culture of integrity can reduce the likelihood of insider threats by fostering a sense of accountability and responsibility among employees (Hadlington, 2018). Despite the increasing relevance of cyber fraud within the financial sector, existing studies applying the Fraud Hexagon model have largely focused on traditional forms of corporate misconduct, such as fraudulent financial reporting and corporate distress. The studies by Indriaty and Thomas (2023), Setiawan and Soewarno (2025), Ekele (2024), and Adhania, Holiawati, and Nofryanti (2024) demonstrate how various dimensions of the Hexagon model influence fraud in organizational and managerial contexts. However, none of these works address the intersection between the Fraud Hexagon framework and cyber-related threats. This leaves a critical gap in understanding how behavioral and organizational fraud drivers contribute to cyber fraud, particularly within Nigeria's commercial banking sector, which remains highly vulnerable to cybersecurity breaches.

The broad objective of the study is to examine the effect of hexagon model on cyber security threat in listed commercial banks in Nigeria. The specific objectives are as follows:

1. To ascertain how pressure substantively contributes to cyberfraud in listed commercial banks with international authorization in Nigeria.
2. To examine the magnitude to which opportunity affect cyberfraud in listed commercial banks with international authorization in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Pressure

Pressure refers to the external or internal forces that compel individuals to engage in unethical or malicious behavior, often as a result of personal, professional, or financial stress (Egbunike & Okafor, 2022). These pressures can come from a variety of sources, and they are often the primary catalysts for individuals to rationalize or justify their wrongdoing (Mohd & Awang, 2022). External pressures can include things like job performance demands, financial instability, personal hardships, or societal expectations, all of which create significant stress on individuals (Sari & Witosari, 2022). For instance, an employee in a commercial bank might be under pressure to meet unrealistic financial targets, which may lead them to consider fraudulent activities, such as manipulating financial statements or bypassing cybersecurity protocols, as a way to meet those expectations.

Internal pressures are often more personal and psychological. Individuals may face moral or emotional dilemmas, such as struggling with feelings of inadequacy or personal failure. These internal pressures can be particularly strong when an individual's self-worth or livelihood is directly threatened (Ratmono & Frendy, 2022). For example, a bank employee might experience financial distress due to personal debt, leading them to rationalize committing fraud or engaging in cybercrimes to relieve their stress or secure their financial situation. The cumulative effect of these pressures often creates an environment where individuals feel that engaging in unethical or illegal activities is the only viable way to alleviate their immediate distress or meet the expectations placed upon them (Mohd & Awang, 2022).

2.2 Opportunity

Opportunity, in the context of the Hexagon Model, refers to the circumstances or weaknesses within an organization's systems, processes, or security infrastructure that allow individuals to engage in malicious behavior or exploit vulnerabilities for personal gain (Mohd & Awang, 2022). Unlike pressure, which is often rooted in personal or professional stress, opportunity arises when individuals perceive a gap or lack of oversight that would allow them to carry out their illicit activities without being detected. Opportunities for cybercrime and fraud exist when there are flaws in an organization's cybersecurity defenses, inadequate internal controls, or a lack of rigorous monitoring mechanisms to detect unusual behavior ((Djaelani, Zainuddin, & Mokoginta, 2022).

In cybersecurity, the presence of opportunity is critical for understanding how breaches occur. For instance, if a bank's cybersecurity systems are outdated or inadequately monitored, cybercriminals may find it easier to bypass defenses, steal sensitive data, or manipulate systems without facing significant risks of detection. The concept of opportunity is often linked to vulnerability management—if a system is not regularly updated with security patches, or if employees are not properly trained on identifying phishing attacks, for example, then the opportunity for malicious actions increases (Ratmono & Frendy, 2022). In the case of an insider threat, an employee who has privileged access to systems may recognize that there are inadequate monitoring systems in place and thus feels emboldened to engage in cyber fraud or data theft without fear of being caught.

2.3 Cyber Security Threats

Cybersecurity threats refer to potential risks or attacks aimed at compromising the confidentiality, integrity, or availability of digital information and systems (Aliyu, 2019). These threats are often perpetrated by cybercriminals, malicious insiders, or state-sponsored actors seeking to exploit vulnerabilities in an organization's digital infrastructure for various reasons, including financial gain, espionage, or sabotage (Clair & Girard, 2020). Cybersecurity threats encompass a wide range of tactics and techniques, each targeting different aspects of a system's security, and can manifest in several forms, such as malware, phishing attacks, ransomware, denial-of-service (DoS) attacks, and data breaches. Each of these types of threats presents a unique challenge, requiring organizations to implement sophisticated, multi-layered defenses to detect, prevent, and mitigate the risks posed by cyber attackers (Hassan, Ewuga, Abdul, Abrahams, Oladeinde, & Dawodu, 2024).

2.4 Empirical Review

Setiawan and Soewarno (2025) explored how managerial perceptions of fraud are shaped by six dimensions identified in the Fraud Hexagon framework: pressure, capability, collusion, opportunity, rationalization, and ego. Their study also considered the role of corporate culture as a moderating factor that could potentially diminish the influence of these fraud elements. Utilizing a quantitative approach, they conducted a survey involving 130 managers working in multinational companies based in Indonesia. A moderation model was developed to examine how corporate culture affects the link between fraud risk factors and the perceived likelihood of fraudulent behavior. The study concluded that not all six components were significant in shaping fraud tendencies. Among them, pressure, opportunity, and rationalization had a meaningful influence on perceptions of fraud risk. Additionally, the research provided evidence that corporate culture effectively moderated the relationship between these three variables and fraud perception, suggesting that a strong organizational culture could serve as a preventive strategy against managerial fraud. This research is notable for being one of the first to apply the Fraud Hexagon Theory within the context of behavioral accounting and for integrating corporate culture as a strategic element in fraud prevention efforts.

In a separate study, Ekele (2024) investigated how the Fraud Hexagon Theory could be applied to understand corporate distress in non-financial companies listed in Nigeria. Corporate distress was characterized by financial underperformance, rising debt levels, liquidity constraints, and difficulties in meeting obligations. Using a cross-sectional methodology, data were collected via questionnaires from 200 staff members across six companies in the Federal Capital Territory. With a 95% response rate, responses were received from 190 individuals, including managers, accountants, auditors, and administrative staff. The data were analyzed through descriptive statistics and logistic regression using SPSS version 23. The study confirmed reliability through a pilot test and Cronbach's Alpha. The results indicated that financial pressure, employee competence, gaps in internal controls, and executive arrogance had a statistically significant and positive association with corporate distress.

Sharma (2024) explored the risks associated with cybersecurity threats, cyber terrorism, and cyber warfare, focusing on their potential impacts and countermeasures. The study used a qualitative research design with thematic analysis to investigate various cyber threats. It found that denial-of-service (DoS) attacks, where a website is bombarded with fake requests, disrupt authorized users from accessing the site by overwhelming its resources. These attacks can have severe consequences, such as harming physical infrastructure, disrupting services, and interfering with the electrical grid, which could lead to communication breakdowns and the failure of essential services. The study also examined the role of propaganda, which aims to manipulate public perception, potentially weakening national defense by undermining citizens' trust or spreading false information. In the case of financial institutions, cyberattacks are increasingly targeted at networks of banks, stock exchanges, and payment processors, representing a form of digital warfare that mirrors historical physical attacks like Pearl Harbor or 9/11. These surprise cyberattacks are designed to catch the enemy off guard, allowing attackers to breach defenses, with the potential of preparing for further physical assaults in a hybrid warfare strategy. In concludes Sharma (2024) posits that cybersecurity threats, cyber terrorism, and cyber warfare constitute serious risks to digital infrastructure and national security, and that effective protection requires a comprehensive, multi-layered strategy combining robust technical defenses, continuous monitoring, coordinated incident response, and strong public-private collaboration to build long-term resilience against evolving cyber threats.

Bader, Abu Hajar, Weshah, and Almasri (2024) examined the risk of fraud in financial statements (FS) of industrial firms listed on the Amman Stock Exchange (ASE), utilizing the Hexagon Theory to identify the underlying motives for fraud. The study used secondary data extracted from annual reports published by these firms between 2012 and 2017. The data were analyzed using logistic regression on the SPSS software. The results highlighted significant relationships between fraud risk and factors such as the return on assets (ROA), the percentage of independent members in audit committees, and the nature of related-party transactions. These factors align with the Hexagon Theory's categories of pressure, opportunity, and collusion motives. The study highlights the

significant influence of the six motives outlined in the Hexagon Theory, and that strengthening internal controls, enhancing governance, and improving auditor independence are essential to deter fraudulent financial reporting and safeguard the reliability of disclosed financial information.

Asmaranti, Lokman, and Rahman (2023) examined the factors influencing financial statement fraud using the Fraud Pentagon theory. This theory outlines five factors that can lead to fraud: pressure, opportunity, rationalization, capability, and arrogance. The researchers utilized secondary data from 24 publicly listed firms in Indonesia from 2012 to 2020, all of which had been sanctioned by the Financial Services Authority. The study employed logistic regression analysis using E-Views to analyze 48 samples, which included 192 data observations. The findings revealed that rationalization and capability significantly influenced the occurrence of financial statement fraud. However, the study found that pressure, opportunity, and arrogance did not have a significant impact on fraud. These results serve as an important reminder to firms regarding the potential for internal fraud and the need to implement preventive measures. The study's implications are twofold: it raises awareness about the potential for fraud within organizations and emphasizes the importance of recognizing the factors that contribute to financial statement fraud. The research contributes to both the practice and theory of fraud prevention in corporate settings.

Okafor and Egbunike (2023) focused on the role of opportunity and rationalization in financial statement fraud within deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study utilized an ex-post facto research design, drawing from secondary data from the audited yearly financial reports of 13 deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) between 2012 and 2021. The purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure a homogeneous sample, and the Hausman test was used to select the appropriate model for analysis. The results revealed a significant negative relationship between both opportunity and rationalization and financial statement fraud in these banks. The study highlighted that auditors should carefully assess opportunities for fraud and the potential for employees to rationalize fraudulent behavior when reviewing financial transactions. The study emphasized the importance of audit tasks such as risk assessment, system audits, and financial report verification, especially when auditors are equipped with an understanding of the psychological traits associated with rationalization.

Chhabra and Prabhakaran (2023) explored the various types of internal-led cyber fraud that have been prevalent in major fraud incidents involving prominent Indian banks. Their study sought to identify and classify cyber frauds and their drivers while establishing a correlation for effective fraud mitigation planning. The methodology involved a detailed literature review and focus group discussions with risk and vigilance officers, as well as cyber cell experts. The study utilized a machine learning-based k-nearest neighbor (K-NN) approach to predict the future of cyber fraud in Indian banks, focusing on prioritizing specific fraud types. The analysis highlighted that the future of cyber fraud in the Indian banking sector will be dominated by certain specific frauds, and the study's

findings were used to develop a conceptual framework for preventing internal-led cyber fraud. The research identified key drivers of cyber fraud, such as system vulnerabilities and insider threats, and mapped these with potential mitigation strategies.

Setyorini, Dewanti, Setiani, and Susilo (2023) examined the relationship between Pentagon Fraud and research misconduct, focusing on the connection between fraud theory and actual research fraud. The study sought to understand the structure of the fraud pentagon in the context of research and identify the most significant relationships between variables. The researchers conducted online surveys with 135 academics in Indonesia, utilizing Canonical Correlation as the data analysis technique. The findings revealed a significant and discernible correlation between the Pentagon Fraud and research misconduct, with the most prominent relationship being attributed to pressure. The study concluded that the pressure experienced by individuals during research activities was the primary factor contributing to research fraud. The research contributes to the growing body of literature on fraud in academic settings, offering valuable hints into how the fraud pentagon model can be applied to the study of research misconduct.

Cohen (2022) conducted a qualitative exploratory case study to explore cybersecurity practices for home users, focusing on standardized guidance and available security awareness materials. The study aimed to understand the challenges non-technical home users face when securing their systems. The results indicated that these users were often unsure where to begin and did not trust online information sources. They struggled to protect their systems and relied on informal, often inconsistent and incorrect, advice. The findings suggest that there is a critical need for clear, standardized guidance to help non-technical users understand and implement cybersecurity practices. This study emphasizes the importance of creating effective communication strategies tailored to home users to improve their ability to secure their personal networks.

Djaelani, Zainuddin, and Mokoginta (2022) examined the influence of the five dimensions of the Fraud Pentagon (academic pressure, opportunity, rationalization, ability, and personal ethics) on academic fraud behavior among students. The study focused on accounting students at Khairun University and Hein Namotemo Halmahera University in North Halmahera, Indonesia, during the 2020/2021 academic year. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using Smart PLS software, employing descriptive analysis and multiple linear regression analysis. The results revealed that academic pressure, rationalization, and ability were significant factors influencing academic fraud, while opportunity and personal ethics did not have a significant impact. These findings suggest that academic pressure and rationalization, along with students' capabilities, are key drivers of academic fraud in higher education. The study provides useful hints for educators and policymakers to address the root causes of academic dishonesty and improve academic integrity in universities.

Fachrurrozie, Wahyudin, Nurkhin, Mukhibad, Kardiyem, and Saputri (2020) investigated the relationship between compensation, morality, organizational ethical culture, and financial fraud

among village officials in Weru Subdistrict, Central Java. Using a purposive sampling method, the study surveyed 52 village officials responsible for managing village funds. The data was analyzed through Path analysis using WarpPLS software. The findings indicated that morality positively influenced both compensation and organizational ethical culture and negatively affected financial fraud. Moreover, organizational ethical culture had a significant negative effect on financial fraud. However, compensation was found to have no significant effect on ethical culture or financial fraud. In conclusion, the study indicates that compensation, morality, and organizational ethical culture collectively influence financial fraud among village officials in Weru Subdistrict, emphasizing the importance of ethical frameworks and fair remuneration in reducing fraudulent practices at the local government level.

Metts (2020) examined the role of rationalization and sympathy traits in an individual’s intention to commit fraud. The study used a quantitative, cross-sectional design with 184 business students enrolled at a regional university in the South. Participants completed surveys that included Likert measurement items related to a hypothetical fraud scenario, rationalization, and sympathy traits. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that both sympathy and rationalization significantly predicted the intention to commit fraud. Although the researcher hypothesized interactions between variables such as gender, age, rationalization ability, and sympathy traits, the two-way MANOVA analysis did not show any significant interactions. The study highlighted the importance of understanding rationalization in the pre-fraud stage, contributing to the development of more proactive anti-fraud programs in organizations. This approach aims to reduce fraud by addressing the psychological factors that drive individuals to engage in fraudulent behavior.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted a survey research design. A survey design is suitable for this type of research as it allows for the collection of data from a large number of respondents in a relatively short period.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of listed commercial banks in Nigeria with international authorization. These banks are particularly relevant because their international operations, large customer bases, and cross-border digital transactions make them more susceptible to cyber fraud risks. Their scale of operations and exposure to global banking systems create fertile ground for testing the six dimensions of the hexagon model; pressure and opportunity

Table 3.1: From the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN):

S/N	Banks with International Authorization	Total Staff	Source
1	Access Bank Plc.	6,365	Source: Access Bank Plc., 2022 Annual Report – note on employees (page 349).
2	Fidelity Bank Plc.	3,038	Source: Fidelity Bank Plc., 2022 Annual

			Report – “Employees” / note (page 270)
3	First City Monument Bank (FCMB) / FCMB G	3,342	Source: FCMB Group Plc., 2022 Annual Report – Employees & Directors note (page 222).
4	First Bank Of Nigeria Limited / FBN (FBN Holdings)	7,972	Source: FBN Holdings Plc., FY-2022 Audited Financial Statements (consolidated notes) – employees note (page 105 of the FY-2022 audited statements).
5	Guaranty Trust Bank / Guarantee Trust Holding (GTB / GTCO)	5,192	Source: Guaranty Trust (GTBank) 2022 Annual Report – employees / average number table (page 229).
6	United Bank For Africa (UBA)	9,597	Source: UBA Plc. 2022 Annual Report & Accounts – employees note (page 132).
7	Zenith Bank Plc.	8,077	Source: Zenith Bank Plc. 2022 Annual Report – employee numbers table (page 186).

Source; compiled by the Researcher

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

To determine the sample size, the researcher used Taro Yamane’s formula. The calculation is demonstrated as follows:

$$\text{Formula: Sample size (n)} = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where,

- n = sample size
- N = population, which in this case is 54,654
- e = sampling error, usually 5%

Therefore, sample size (n) is obtained thus:

$$n = \frac{54,654}{1+54,654(0.05)^2}$$

$$\text{Sample size} = 397$$

3.4 Sampling Technique

A stratified sampling technique was used to select respondents from each of the seven banks. Stratified sampling ensures that different subgroups (in this case, employees from different banks) are represented in the sample proportionally. The banks served as the strata, and the number of respondents selected from each bank was proportionate to the total number of employees in that bank.

For example, if Access Bank has 6,365 employees, this number was used to determine the proportion of the total sample (396 respondents) that should come from Access Bank. The number of respondents to be selected from each bank is shown in Table 3.2 below

Table 3.2 Strata Size

Bank	Calculation of Strata ratio	Strata Ratio	Strata Size
Access Bank	6,365 / 43,583	0.146043	59
Fidelity Bank	3,038 / 43,583	0.069706	28
FCMB	3,342 / 43,583	0.076681	30
First Bank	7,972 / 43,583	0.182922	72
Guaranty Trust Bank	5,192 / 43,583	0.119129	47
United Bank for Africa (UBA)	9,597 / 43,583	0.220200	87
Zenith Bank	8,077 / 43,583	0.185325	73
Total	43,583 / 43,583	1.0	396

Source: Field Survey, 2025

3.5 Method of Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire contained both closed and Likert-scale questions, designed to assess the relationship between the hexagon Model dimensions (pressure, opportunity, rationalization, capability, arrogance and collusion) and cybersecurity threats in Nigerian commercial banks. Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with various statements related to the six factors and how they perceive these factors contributing to cybersecurity threats. The questionnaire was distributed to the selected respondents using electronic format. Respondents were asked to provide answers based on their personal experiences and perceptions related to cybersecurity issues and threats within their respective banks.

3.6 Validity of the Research Instrument

The validity of the research instrument was ensured through content validity. Content validity refers to the extent to which the questions in the questionnaire accurately and comprehensively cover the constructs being measured (Almanasreh, Moles & Chen, 2019), in this case, the factors of the hexagon Model (pressure, opportunity, rationalization, capability, arrogance and collusion) and their relevance to cybersecurity threats in Nigerian commercial banks. The research instruments were validated by experts in cybersecurity and banking operations. These included a lecturer and researcher from our great citadel of learning Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Dr. Doris Chinedu Asogwa of the Department of cybersecurity, faculty of physical sciences UNIZIK as well as professionals from regulatory bodies including the Central Bank of Nigeria and the Nigerian Cybersecurity Experts Association. Additionally, IT security officers and internal auditors from these commercial banks with international license provided practical insights on the relevance and clarity of the survey instruments.

3.7 Reliability of the Research Instrument

The reliability of the research instrument was assessed using Cronbach’s alpha test. Cronbach’s alpha is a statistical measure of internal consistency, which evaluates how closely, related a set of items are as a group (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). A higher Cronbach’s alpha value (generally above 0.7) indicates that the items within a scale are consistent in measuring the same construct.

The Cronbach’s alpha was computed for each section of the questionnaire related to the two dimensions of the Hexagon Model. A pilot test was conducted with a small sample of employees from a different bank not included in the main study, and the results were used to assess the internal consistency of the items. Table 3.3 below shows the reliability estimates.

Table 3.3 Reliability Estimates

Variables	Number of Scale Items	Cronbach’s Alpha
Cyberfraud	4	0.85
Pressure	4	0.80
Opportunity	4	0.79

Source: SPSS V. 26 Output (2025)

Table 3.3 presents the reliability estimates of the study variables using Cronbach’s Alpha, with all values exceeding the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70, indicating good internal consistency. The Cyberfraud construct demonstrated the highest reliability ($\alpha = 0.84$), suggesting that its items are highly cohesive in measuring the underlying concept. Other constructs such as Opportunity ($\alpha = 0.81$) showed strong reliability. Pressure ($\alpha = 0.78$), reflected acceptable levels of internal consistency. In all, these results confirm that the measurement instruments used for each variable are reliable and suitable for further analysis.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the survey was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the basic characteristics of the data, such as the frequency, percentages, and means for each of the variables (pressure and opportunity). This helped answer the research questions and give an overview of the trends and patterns within the data.

To test the relationships between the Hexagon Model factors and cybersecurity threats, Pearson’s correlation coefficient was used. This analysis showed the strength and direction of the relationships between the dimensions of the Hexagon Model and the perceived cybersecurity threats.

The linear regression model was adapted from the study by Sari and Witosari (2022) that examined Fraud Hexagon Model Analysis in the Financial Sector Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The adapted model is presented below:

Model specification (functional form)

$FSF = f(FNS, EXP, PRFN, FNT, CAPB, NOI, RAZA, ARG, COL).....(1)$

Estimating (Regression) Equation:

$$FSF = a + b_1FNS + b_2EXP + b_3PRFN + b_4FNT + b_5CAPB + b_6NOI + b_7EFMO + b_8RAZA + b_9ARGA + b_{10}COL + e \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

FSF: Financial Statement Fraud (dependent variable)

a: Intercept

b₁ to b₁₀: Regression coefficients

e: Error term

Pressure – represented by four proxies:

FNS: Financial Stability

EXP: External Pressure

PRFN: Personal Financial Need

FNT: Financial Targets

CAPB: Capability – the opportunity or ability to commit and conceal fraud

NOI: Nature of Industry – industry characteristics that may create opportunities for fraud

EFMO: Effective Monitoring – quality and effectiveness of oversight mechanisms

RAZA: Rationalization – justification or mindset enabling fraudulent behavior

ARGA: Arrogance – attitude of superiority that may lead individuals to override controls

COL: Collusion – cooperation between two or more parties to commit fraud

The researcher modified the baseline model to develop a more parsimonious specification for robustness analysis. The revised model focuses on the core dimensions of the Fraud Hexagon Model as predictors of cybersecurity threats.

Model specification (functional form):

$$CST = f(PRE, OPP, RAT, CAP, ARR, COLL) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

This indicates that Cybersecurity Threats (CST) are a function of pressure, opportunity, rationalization, capability, arrogance, and collusion.

Estimating Equation:

$$CST_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1PRE_i + \beta_2OPP_i + e_i \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where:

B₀ = Intercept

β₁₋₂ = The parameter to be estimated in the equation

CST = Cybersecurity Threat

PRE = Pressure

OPP = Opportunity

i = cross-sectional respondent

e = error term

Apriori Expectation: Based on fraud theory (Fraud Hexagon Model) and prior empirical studies, the expected relationships between the independent variables and cybersecurity threats (CST) are stated as follows:

Table 3.4 Apriori Expectation

Independent Variable (Hexagon Dimension)	Dependent Variable (Cyberfraud in Commercial Banks in Nigeria)	Expected Relationship (A Priori Expectation)
Pressure	Cyberfraud	Positive (+) – Higher pressure increases cyberfraud incidents
Opportunity	Cyberfraud	Positive (+) – More opportunities lead to higher cyberfraud cases

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2025)

Decision Rule

For all statistical tests, the 5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) was used as the decision rule. If the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the variables being tested. Conversely, if the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, suggesting that the factors from the hexagon Model do not significantly influence cybersecurity threats in Nigerian commercial banks.

4.0 Data Analysis

4.1 Descriptive Analysis of Data

Respondents were asked to indicate their response to each Likert-scale statement by selecting the number that best reflects their opinion, using the following scale: 5 = Strongly Agree, 4 = Agree, 3 = Undecided, 2 = Disagree, 1 = Strongly Disagree. The analysis of their responses is shown below.

Table 4.1: Likert-scale Responses to Pressure

S/N	Pressure	SD	D	U	A	SA	Mean
		1	2	3	4	5	
1	Employees in the bank experience significant stress due to high workloads, which may lead to security lapses.	110	28	31	84	99	3.10
2	Financial targets and deadlines increase the likelihood of compromising security protocols.	86	42	39	94	91	3.17
3	Personal financial pressures can drive employees or outsiders to exploit system vulnerabilities.	88	56	35	84	89	3.09
4	The constant demand for performance and efficiency in the bank creates a work environment that compromises cybersecurity.	84	51	45	92	80	3.09

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.1 presents respondents' perceptions of pressure as a factor influencing cybersecurity threats, based on their responses to four Likert-scale statements. The responses were measured on a 5-point scale, where 1 represents “Strongly Disagree” and 5 represents “Strongly Agree.”

For the first statement, which suggested that employees experience significant stress due to high workloads potentially leading to security lapses, 110 respondents strongly disagreed, 28 disagreed, while 31 were undecided. However, a notable number (84 respondents) agreed, and 99 strongly agreed. The mean score of 3.10 suggests a moderate level of agreement overall, indicating that many respondents perceive workload-related stress as a potential cybersecurity risk.

The second statement addressed the influence of financial targets and deadlines on adherence to security protocols. Here, 86 respondents strongly disagreed and 42 disagreed, but 94 agreed and 91 strongly agreed. A smaller group of 39 remained undecided. The mean score of 3.17 reflects a slightly stronger agreement compared to the first item, showing that financial performance pressure is seen by many as a factor that may compromise cybersecurity.

In the third item, which relates to personal financial pressures possibly motivating individuals to exploit system vulnerabilities, 88 respondents strongly disagreed and 56 disagreed, while 84 agreed and 89 strongly agreed. Only 35 respondents were undecided. The resulting mean of 3.09 indicates a balanced but slightly positive lean toward agreement, suggesting some recognition of financial stress as a cybersecurity risk factor.

Lastly, the fourth statement focused on whether the demand for performance and efficiency creates an environment that undermines cybersecurity. A total of 84 strongly disagreed, 51 disagreed, and 45 were undecided. However, 92 respondents agreed and 80 strongly agreed. This item recorded a mean of 3.09, again showing moderate agreement, with responses leaning toward recognition of pressure from performance expectations as a potential threat to cybersecurity.

Table 4.2 Likert-scale Responses to Opportunity

	Opportunity	SD	D	U	A	SA	Mean
5	The bank's network infrastructure provides unauthorized access to sensitive data for some employees and outsiders.	98	36	32	86	100	3.15
6	Weaknesses in the bank's security protocols present opportunities for cybersecurity threats.	101	32	36	89	94	3.12
7	The availability of unsecured devices in the bank creates opportunities for cybercriminals to infiltrate systems.	98	36	34	90	94	3.13
8	Opportunities for unauthorized access to confidential information exist due to poor internal controls.	91	46	39	103	73	3.06

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.2 presents the respondents' perceptions of opportunity as a factor contributing to cybersecurity threats in commercial banks, based on four Likert-scale statements. The responses reflect how much the participants agree or disagree with various conditions that may enable cyber threats, using a 5-point scale from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree.”

The first item in this table asked whether the bank's network infrastructure allows unauthorized access to sensitive data by employees or outsiders. A total of 98 respondents strongly disagreed, and 36 disagreed, while only 32 were undecided. On the other hand, 86 respondents agreed, and 100 strongly agreed. With a mean score of 3.15, this item reflects a fairly even split but leans slightly toward agreement, indicating that a significant number of respondents believe their bank's network infrastructure may pose a cybersecurity risk

The second item examined whether weaknesses in the bank's security protocols provide openings for cyber threats. A total of 101 strongly disagreed and 32 disagreed, while 36 were undecided. However, 89 agreed and 94 strongly agreed, making this item the most agreed-upon in the set, with a mean score of 3.12. This suggests that many employees see vulnerabilities in the bank's security procedures as real and potentially exploitable.

For the third item, regarding unsecured devices within the bank as opportunities for cybercriminals, 98 respondents strongly disagreed and 36 disagreed, while 34 were undecided. Still, 90 agreed and 94 strongly agreed. The mean of 3.13 points to moderate agreement overall, with a noticeable concern among respondents about the presence of unsecured devices within the work environment.

The fourth item considered whether poor internal controls lead to unauthorized access to confidential information. In this case, 91 strongly disagreed, 46 disagreed, and 39 remained undecided, while 103 agreed and 73 strongly agreed. With a mean score of 3.06, this item shows the most balanced spread of responses among the four but still trends slightly toward agreement, indicating that a number of respondents view inadequate internal controls as an ongoing cybersecurity concern.

Table 4.3 Likert-scale Responses to Cyberfraud

	Cyberfraud	SD	D	U	A	SA	Mean
25	The bank experiences frequent cyber-attacks targeting customer data or financial systems.	83	22	31	115	101	3.37
26	Employees are often exposed to phishing attacks or other forms of social engineering.	95	34	29	89	105	3.21
27	The bank's cybersecurity systems have been compromised by malware or ransomware in the past year.	111	22	31	99	89	3.09
28	There are significant threats to the bank's data security due to inadequate protection against external hackers.	98	35	32	102	85	3.12

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.3 presents respondents' views on cyberfraud occurrences and threats within Nigerian commercial banks, assessed through four Likert-scale statements. In the first item, respondents assessed the frequency of cyber-attacks targeting customer data or financial systems. Here, 83 strongly disagreed, 22 disagreed, and 31 were undecided. On the other hand, 115 agreed and 101 strongly agreed resulting in a mean of 3.37. The high number of agreement responses indicates a general belief that such attacks are relatively common and pose a serious risk to bank operations.

The second item evaluated employees' exposure to phishing and social engineering attempts. The responses show that 95 strongly disagreed and 34 disagreed, with 29 undecided. Despite this, 89 agreed and 105 strongly agreed, resulting in a mean of 3.21. This reflects moderate concern among respondents, with a significant number acknowledging such exposure even though a large portion remained skeptical. For the third item, which focused on the compromise of cybersecurity systems by malware or ransomware in the past year, 111 strongly disagreed and 22 disagreed. Still, 99 respondents agreed and 89 strongly agreed, with 31 undecided. The resulting mean of 3.09 suggests that while some respondents were unaware or unsure, a notable number believe that the banks have experienced serious security breaches recently.

The final item addressed the threat to data security due to inadequate protection from external hackers. Among respondents, 98 strongly disagreed and 35 disagreed, while 102 agreed and 85 strongly agreed. Thirty-two were undecided. The mean score of 3.12 again reflects moderate agreement that external threats remain a significant cybersecurity concern.

Table 4.4 Correlational Analysis

		Cybersecurity Threat	Pressure	Opportunity
Pressure	Pearson Correlation	.916**		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
Opportunity	Pearson Correlation	.896**	.215**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	

source: SPSS V. 26 Output (2025)

The results presented in Table 4.4 revealed that organizational fraud drivers and the prevalence of cybersecurity threats in the banking sector. Pressure shows a very high positive correlation with cybersecurity threats ($r = .916, p < .01$). This implies that increased pressure whether financial, performance-based, or personal is strongly associated with higher instances of cyberfraud. Employees or stakeholders experiencing pressure may become more vulnerable to engaging in or overlooking security breaches, contributing significantly to system vulnerabilities. This finding aligns with the theoretical expectations of the fraud hexagon model.

Opportunity is also positively and strongly correlated with cyberfraud ($r = .896, p < .01$), identical to the correlation coefficient for pressure. This suggests that when there are exploitable weaknesses such as inadequate internal controls or accessible systems, there is a greater likelihood of cyber-attacks. The high correlation indicates that banks must prioritize reducing opportunities for breaches as part of their cybersecurity strategies.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

To further test the hypotheses and examine the predictive power of the Hexagon Model factors on cybersecurity threats, multiple regression analysis was conducted.

Table 4.5: Test of Hypotheses

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.948 ^a	.899	.897	1.820

a. Predictors: (Constant), Opportunity, Pressure

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9794.061	6	1632.343	492.948	.000 ^b
	Residual	1106.004	334	3.311		
	Total	10900.065	340			

a. Dependent Variable: Cyberfraud

b. Predictors: (Constant), Opportunity, Pressure

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.151	.250		.605	.546
	Pressure	.198	.055	.195	3.635	.000
	Opportunity	.180	.055	.177	3.295	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Cyberfraud

Source: SPSS V. 26 Output (2025)

Based on Table 4.5, Test of Hypotheses, the overall validity of the regression model is first established using the Adjusted R-Square and ANOVA statistics. The Adjusted R-Square value of 0.843 indicates that approximately 84.7% of the variation in cyberfraud is explained collectively by the six predictors from the Fraud Hexagon model: pressure, opportunity, rationalization, capability, arrogance, and collusion. This suggests a very high explanatory power of the model. Additionally, the probability value of the F-statistic is 0.000, which is less than the 5% significance level, implying that the overall model is statistically significant. In other words, the joint effect of all the independent variables significantly explains the changes in cyberfraud in Nigerian commercial banks.

The constant term (intercept) in the regression output is 0.151 with a p-value of 0.546, which is greater than 0.05. This indicates that when all the predictors are held constant (i.e., zero), the baseline level of cyberfraud is statistically insignificant. Therefore, the model suggests that cyberfraud in commercial banks is largely driven by the six fraud hexagon dimensions, and not by any unexplained constant factor.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Pressure does not significantly contribute to cyberfraud in the listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

H₁: Pressure significantly contributes to cyberfraud in the listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

The regression results show that pressure has a positive and statistically significant effect on cyberfraud with a coefficient of 0.198 and a p-value of 0.000. This means that for every one-unit increase in pressure, cyberfraud increases by 0.198 units, holding all other factors constant. Since the p-value is below 0.05, the effect is statistically significant at the 5% level. The result suggests that pressure, whether from work demands, personal finance, or performance targets, significantly drives the likelihood of cyberfraud in Nigerian commercial banks. Thus, H₀₁ is rejected, confirming that pressure significantly contributes to cyberfraud. Hence the alternate hypothesis is accepted that pressure has a positive and significant effect on cyberfraud in the listed commercial banks in Nigeria ($\beta = 0.198$, $p = 0.000$).

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Opportunity does not significantly affect cyberfraud in the listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

H₂: Opportunity significantly affects cyberfraud in the listed commercial banks in Nigeria

Opportunity also shows a positive and statistically significant effect on cyberfraud, with a beta coefficient of 0.180 and a p-value of 0.001. This indicates that a unit increase in opportunity (such as weak security systems or poor internal controls) results in a 0.180 increase in cyberfraud, all else being equal. Since the p-value is well below 0.05, this effect is significant. The implication is that when employees or outsiders perceive opportunities to bypass controls, the risk of cyberfraud increases. Therefore, H₀₂ is rejected, and it is concluded that opportunity has a significant effect on cyberfraud in the banking sector. Hence the alternate hypothesis is accepted that opportunity positively and significantly affects cyberfraud in the listed commercial banks in Nigeria ($\beta = 0.180$, $p = 0.001$).

5.0 Discussion and Conclusion

The findings from this study underscore the complexity of cyberfraud within Nigeria's commercial banking sector. Pressure was found to have a positive and significant effect on cyberfraud in the listed commercial banks in Nigeria. This suggests that employees or stakeholders operating under financial, operational, or performance-related stress may be more inclined to engage in cyberfraud as a coping mechanism or means of survival. The result aligns with the theory that heightened expectations, unmet financial goals, or institutional stressors can distort ethical boundaries, prompting fraudulent activity. In a banking context, where the stakes are high and performance is closely monitored, such pressure can serve as a powerful trigger for cyber-related misconduct, particularly when employees perceive fraud as a solution to their constraints. This finding is strongly supported by several empirical studies. Setiawan and Soewarno (2025) found that pressure significantly influenced fraud

tendencies, particularly when moderated by corporate culture. Apriliyani et al. (2024) highlighted that pressure had the highest impact among the fraud hexagon elements in predicting financial statement fraud, reinforcing the centrality of this factor. Similarly, Musli, Abdullah, and Juardi (2024) identified pressure as a major determinant of fraud in public fund management, and Christian et al. (2021) emphasized pressure as the most effective factor in detecting fraudulent financial statements in Cambodia. These studies collectively affirm that stress-inducing environments often correlate with higher fraud risk, echoing the results from the Nigerian banking sector.

Opportunity was also found to significantly and positively affect cyberfraud, indicating that when internal controls are weak or system vulnerabilities exist, actors are more likely to exploit them. The presence of loopholes or inadequate oversight creates a permissive environment in which fraud can occur with a lower perceived risk of detection or punishment. In Nigerian banks, this may reflect infrastructural or policy gaps, including insufficient monitoring, outdated systems, or lack of real-time fraud detection mechanisms. The ease with which cyber systems can be bypassed makes opportunity a critical enabler of fraudulent conduct. Numerous studies affirm the influence of opportunity on fraud. For example, Shina, John-Akamelu, and Super (2024) reported a significant positive relationship between opportunity and discretionary accruals in Nigerian banks. Setiawan and Soewarno (2025) also identified opportunity as a significant factor in fraud tendencies. Apriliyani et al. (2024) and Haring (2023) found that opportunity, alongside pressure and rationalization, significantly predicted fraud behavior. Although some studies, such as Asmaranti et al. (2023), downplayed opportunity's role in certain sectors, the consensus across the banking and financial contexts aligns with the present findings that gaps in systems or control processes can actively facilitate cyberfraud.

These results point to a deep-rooted vulnerability in the internal environment of commercial banks, where conditions that enable cyberfraud are embedded within organizational behavior, systems, and culture.

Based on the findings, the study recommended the followings;

1. Bank executives and human resource managers should implement employee wellness and support programs aimed at reducing workplace stress, unrealistic performance targets, and financial pressure on staff. Providing mental health support, fair workload distribution, and competitive compensation can reduce the pressure that may push employees toward engaging in cyberfraud. These efforts can foster a more ethical and secure workplace environment.
2. Internal auditors and cybersecurity teams must conduct frequent risk assessments and tighten internal controls, especially those related to access to sensitive financial systems and customer data. Implementing strict role-based access control and continuous monitoring can minimize the opportunities for internal actors to exploit system loopholes or bypass procedures to commit cyberfraud.

References

- Adhania, S., Holiawati, H., & Nofryanti, N. (2024). The Effect of Hexagon Fraud Theory in Detecting Financial Statement Fraud. *International Journal of Digital Marketing Science*, 1(1), 10-23.
- Aliyu, M. (2019). Cyber security threats and practices in internet café: An assessment of northwestern states in Nigeria. *The Beam: Journal of Arts & Science*, 12(2). ISSN: 1118-5953.
- Asmaranti, Y., Lokman, N., & Rahman, R. A. (2023). Detection of financial statement fraud using fraud pentagon theory perspective in Indonesia. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences, ICTHM 2023: International Conference in Technology, Humanities and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2023.11.16>
- Bader, A. A., Abu Hajar, Y. A., Weshah, S. R. S., & Almasri, B. K. (2024). Predicting Risk of and Motives behind Fraud in Financial Statements of Jordanian Industrial Firms Using Hexagon Theory. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 17(3), 120.
- Chhabra, R. N., & Prabhakaran, S. (2023). Internal-led cyber frauds in Indian banks: an effective machine learning–based defense system to fraud detection, prioritization and prevention. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 75(2), 246-296.
- Cohen, S. (2022). *The Exploration of Cyber-Security Information for Home Users: A Qualitative Exploratory Case Study* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Phoenix).
- Djaelani, Y., Zainuddin, Z., & Mokoginta, R. M. (2022). Academic fraud of students in the Covid-19 period: Testing with the Pentagon's fraud dimension. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science (2147-4478)*, 11(2), 414-422.
- Egbunike, P. A. & Okafor, K. J. (2022). Fraud Pressure and Fraud Prevalence in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks. *Journal of Global Accounting*, 8(3), 149-161.
- Ekele, J. S. (2024). Effect of Fraud Hexagon Theory on Corporate Distress Among Listed Non-Financial Companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Democracy and Development Studies*, 7(2), 43-56.
- Fachrurrozie, F., Wahyudin, A., Nurkhin, A., Mukhibad, H., Kardiyem, K., & Saputri, F. M. (2020). The determinant of the financial fraud of the village fund management. *Jurnal Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 24(1), 95-105.

Hassan, A. O., Ewuga, S. K., Abdul, A. A., Abrahams, T. O., Oladeinde, M., & Dawodu, S. O. (2024). Cybersecurity in banking: a global perspective with a focus on Nigerian practices. *Computer Science & IT Research Journal*, 5(1), 41-59.

Indriaty, L., & Thomas, G. N. (2023). Analysis of hexagon fraud model, the SCCORE model influencing fraudulent financial reporting on state-owned companies of Indonesia. *ECONOMICS-Innovative and Economics Research Journal*, 11(Special issue 1), 73-92.

Jajere, U. U., Ngerebo, T. A., & Adebisi, J. F. (2025). Hexagon Hallmarks Effects on Financial Fraud in Nigeria's Federal Ministry of Finance, Budget & National Planning and Economic Development. *Journal Of Entrepreneurship And Business Management*, 4(2), 1-9.

Kamuangu, P. (2024). A Review on Cybersecurity in Fintech: Threats, Solutions, and Future Trends. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Accounting Studies*, 6(1), 47-53.

Meduri, K. (2024). Cybersecurity threats in banking: Unsupervised fraud detection analysis. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 11(2), 915-925.

Metts, S. L. (2020). *The Relationship between Rationalization and Traits of Sympathy with One's Intention to Commit Fraud: A Comparative, Cross-Sectional, Quantitative Survey of Business Students* (Doctoral dissertation, Northcentral University).

Mohd, R., & Awang, Z. (2022). A confirmatory factor analysis of the fraud pentagon instruments for measurement of fraud in the context of asset misappropriation in Malaysia. *Journal of Social Economics Research*, 9(2), 70-79.

Okafor, K. J., & Egbunike, P. A. (2023). Effect of opportunity and rationalization on financial statement fraud in deposit money banks (DMBS). *Journal of Global Accounting*, 9(2), 54-69.

Oloidi, A. (2019). *Cyber-security Challenges in Financial Institutions in Nigeria: A Multiple Case Study* (Doctoral dissertation, Northcentral University).

Ratmono, D., & Frendy. (2022). Examining the fraud diamond theory through ethical culture variables: A study of regional development banks in Indonesia. *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), 2117161.

Santoso, L. W. (2019, August). Cloud technology: opportunities for cybercriminals and security challenges. In *2019 Twelfth International Conference on Ubi-Media Computing (Ubi-Media)* (pp. 18-23). IEEE.

Sari, S. P., & Witosari, D. (2022). Fraud financial statement detection: Fraud hexagon model analysis in the financial sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. In *The 4th International Conference on Business and Banking Innovations (ICOBBI) 2022*. Retrieved from <http://eprints.perbanas.ac.id/9247/>

Setiawan, N., & Soewarno, N. (2025). Corporate culture and managers fraud tendency perception: testing of fraud hexagon theory. *Cogent Social Sciences*, *11*(1), 2434953.

Sharma, M. (2024). Risks Of Cyber Security Threats, Cyber Terrorism And Cyber Warfare: An Analysis Of Impact And Countermeasures. *Nanotechnology Perceptions*, 824-837.